

GRAPHITE FIBRES - THE EXPANDING SCOPE OF

APPLICATIONS IN THE INDUSTRIAL MARKET

Edward M. Trewin
Technical Services Manager
Courtaulds Ltd., Carbon Fibres Unit,
Coventry, England.

Introduction

The commercial utilisation of graphite fibre reinforced plastics (GFRP) continues to expand. New applications demonstrate the challenge now offered by GFRP in a variety of forms to other engineering materials. Basic production costs have reduced considerably over the last five years and graphite composites are competing cost effectively with metals and other engineering plastics through improved performance, increased productivity, longer service life and lower component maintenance.

The paper reviews a number of the commercially successful applications in the industrial sphere, highlighting the effective use of graphite, both in terms of performance and cost. The applications have been selected to illustrate the influence of material performance, material cost, product applicability and processability on the effectiveness of the composite component in competition with conventional materials.

Factors Influencing Growth

Although developed originally for aerospace it has been the commercial application of graphite or carbon fibres that has provided the main outlet and has led to the very substantial increase in world output over the past five years. The commercial utilisation expanded dramatically in 1973 with the advent of the graphite golf shaft which probably still represents the best known material application. Since that time the expansion in volume usage has continued in both aerospace and leisure goods industries consuming the major part of world production estimated at the present time to be around 300 tonnes per annum.

It may seem surprising that sports goods should now be consuming tonnage quantities of fibre whilst aerospace, particularly in Europe, continues to evaluate and consider. However both areas of application have performance requirements which can be matched by the unique properties of GFRP and so it is natural that the enormous potential of the material should be exploited to the full.

Most manufacturers feel that the true volume use for graphite fibres lies eventually in the industrial market. It is therefore most encouraging to observe the growth of applications in the sphere of general engineering and industrial machinery, fulfilling much of the promise indicated in early prototype development work, particularly in textile machinery (1, 2, 3, 4, 5). Indeed this gradual development into more lasting end uses may prove even more significant than the golf shaft breakthrough. There are three main factors influencing the growth of industrial applications.

Material Performance

The unique combination of mechanical properties offered by the material (Table I). The specific strength and stiffness characteristics are already well known, however other features such as low thermal expansion, fatigue resistance, electrical and thermal conductivity, wear resistance, low coefficient of friction, are now being exploited and are extending the range of applications which can benefit from GFRP.

Material	SG	UTS	E	Specific Properties	
				UTS/SG	E/SG
		GPa	GPa	GPa	GPa
A-S/Epoxy*	1.5	1.5	110	1.00	74
HT-S/Epoxy*	1.5	1.9	130	1.27	87
HM-S/Epoxy*	1.6	1.5	190	0.94	119
GRP	2.0	1.0	42	0.50	21
Steel	7.8	1.0	210	0.13	27
Titanium DTD5I73	4.5	0.96	110	0.21	25
Aluminium L65	2.8	0.47	75	0.17	26

Key: 1 GPa = 145 x 10³ lbf/m²
 SG = Specific Gravity
 UTS = Ultimate Tensile Strength
 E = Tensile Modulus

Table I. The properties of unidirectional Graphite Fibre Composites compared with those of other structural materials.

Material Costs

Basic production costs of high modulus graphite fibres have reduced considerably by virtue of increased output coupled with improved manufacturing technology. Today's unit prices from one major European manufacturer are less than 2/5ths those quoted five years ago and the comparison is even more significant when production quantities are considered. This price pattern is the reverse of the trends in other industrial raw materials

further increasing the effect of a downward drift in fibre price.

Product Range

The commercial range of raw materials and derived products is extensive, applicable to a wide variety of processing techniques for component production and capable of meeting diverse performance requirements in composite form.

Products

In order to achieve cost effective performance from graphite composites it is vital that an efficient fabrication technique is employed appropriate to the individual component requirements. Fabrication efficiency is influenced by the form of raw material used and the graphite fibre products available today are the results of considerable development effort aimed at meeting the fabricators need for high quality materials that are convenient to handle with good mechanical performance in composite.

The applications illustrated in the paper concentrate on three available forms, selected for their versatility, performance and growth potential.

Preimpregnated Broadgoods (Prepregs)

Prepregs are available in a wide choice of resin matrices, such as polyester, phenolic, epoxy, polyimide and other thermostable systems. Advanced prepreg systems can be tailored to suit a specific application.

Reinforced Thermoplastic Moulding Materials

The development of a comprehensive range of graphite fibre reinforced thermoplastics has opened up completely new areas of application and components now in production demonstrate the cost effective use of graphite fibres competitive with both metals and engineering plastics. The problems of incorporating graphite fibres into easily processed thermoplastics are being overcome and the technology involving presentation of the fibres in a form convenient for compounding with a variety of matrices is established. Fibre presentation is critical in determining compounding efficiency and influences the performance of the reinforced polymer in a moulded component.

The compounds are supplied in granular form for processing on conventional injection moulding equipment. They are based on high performance polymers including polyamide, polysulphone, polyphenylene sulphide, polycarbonate, polyester, ETFE copolymer and PVDF (polyvinylidene difluoride). Reinforcement levels range from 10 to 50 parts by mass and specially lubricated grades are also available.

Performance details for one particular range of products are given in Table 2. The mechanical and physical characteristics of graphite fibre reinforced thermoplastics (6) (7) offer considerable advantages over other reinforced materials and in some respects their performance is competitive with metals and alloys used as engineering materials, illustrated in Table 3. Individually the performance benefits are impressive but when a combination of properties is considered, then graphite reinforced thermoplastics open up possibilities for applications in areas not hitherto regarded as candidate for engineering plastics.

Property	Units	Nylon 6.6 + 20% GRAFIL A-S	Nylon 6.6 + 30% GRAFIL A-S	Nylon 6.6 + 30% Glass Fibre	Unrein- forced Polymer
<u>Physical:</u>					
Specific Gravity	-	1.23	1.28	1.37	1.14
Water Absorbtion (24 hr immersion)	%	0.6	0.5	0.9	1.5
Mould shrinkage	%	0.25	0.2	0.9	1.5
<u>Mechanical:</u>					
Tensile Strength	MPa	I93	24I	I79	8I
Tensile Elongation	%	3-4	3-4	3-4	IO
Flexural Strength	MPa	289	35I	262	IO3
Flexural Modulus	GPa	I6.5	20	9	2.8
Shear Strength	MPa	82	89	93	66
<u>Thermal:</u>					
Deflection Temp. at 1.80 MN/m ²	°C	257	257	245	66
Coeff. of linear thermal expansion	10 ⁻⁶ /°K	25	I9	32	8I
Thermal Conductivity	W/m°K	0.79	0.95	0.52	0.24

Table 2. Typical properties of GRAFIL*-Thermocomp+ reinforced thermoplastics.

*GRAFIL is the registered trademark of Courtaulds Ltd.

+Thermocomp is the registered trademark of LNP Corporation.

Property	Units	RCI006 (I)	RFI006 (2)	Al	Mg	Zn
Flexural Modulus	G.Pa	20	9	69	47	4I
Flexural Strength	M.Pa	35I	262	I2I	IO3	-
Tensile Strength	M.Pa	24I	I79	I65	227	283
Coefficient Linear Thermal Expansion	10 ⁻⁵ /K	I.9	3.2	2.2	2.5	2.7
Specific Gravity		I.28	I.37	2.89	I.8I	6.6I
Specific Flexural Modulus	G.Pa	I5.6	6.6	23.9	26.0	6.2

Table 3. Properties of fibre reinforced thermoplastics compared with other engineering materials.

(I) RCI006 - 30% graphite fibre in nylon 6.6.

(2) RFI006 - 30% glass fibre in nylon 6.6.

Pultruded Composites Profiles

The technique of pultrusion for the production of low cost composite profiles is now well established, providing high quality, high performance GFRP in a wide variety of cross sectional shapes. Excellent fibre alignment and distribution are achieved in composites containing up to 65% by volume unidirectional fibre reinforcement. Mechanical performance is competitive with stock produced by other more costly moulding procedures and enables the user to incorporate advanced composites into production components without the need for substantial investment (financial or technological) in involved processing procedures. With some allowance made for material anisotropy, most common engineering operations (including adhesive bonding) can be applied to pultruded stock and end-use can be achieved by the composite in its own right or as a reinforcement for other materials.

Cost Effectiveness

A direct material cost comparison between GFRP and other materials is unfavourable, however it is cost effectiveness rather than actual cost that determines the success and viability of a component in production. Indeed, cost effectiveness is the primary consideration in pursuing any application for GFRP in the industrial sphere.

In the applications developed so far the high materials cost can be offset by specific advantages in performance, or by savings in manufacturing costs, or by a combination of these two. In terms of performance, the graphite composite component meets a requirement or set of requirements no other material can, leading to improved productivity by virtue of more efficient operation, lower maintenance and longer service life.

The use of new manufacturing techniques for component fabrication made possible by the availability of graphite fibre reinforced products has introduced dramatic cost savings. For instance, injection moulding capable of providing mass-produced, precision-finished items has eliminated the expensive metal finishing operations necessary with existing manufacturing methods.

Applications

Following on from the dramatic breakthrough of the graphite golf shaft in 1973, the commercial market for GFRP has continued to expand in the leisure goods industry with tennis racquets, skis, ski poles, fishing rods and many others now in volume production. At the same time there is growing acceptance of advanced composite materials in aerospace production components, fulfilling the early promise for extensive use of GFRP in aircraft structures.

The industrial market too is now becoming significant and the rate of growth in this area is particularly encouraging. A number of industrial machinery applications are currently in volume production. The components described in this paper have been selected to illustrate the points made in the previous sections in respect of performance and cost effectiveness.

Yarn Traverse Guide for Textile Processing Machine

The three component traverse guide illustrated in Figure I is moulded from graphite fibre reinforced Nylon 6.6. It replaces a moulding manufactured from unreinforced polyamide and creates a potential for a 25% increase in machine operation. The guide plate, activated by a cam scroll and follower, traverses along a steel spindle at speeds up to 240 metres/minute with high speed reversal. Yarn passing through the ceramic eye in the guide arm is distributed onto a collection package by the traversing action of the guide.

Friction and wear between the guide plate and spindle limit the traversing speed and can cause uneven yarn distribution on the collection package. The superior friction and wear characteristics of the graphite fibre reinforced component coupled with the ability to conduct heat of friction rapidly away from the rubbing face enables higher speeds to be operated, increasing the traverse rate from 360 to over 450 double strokes per minute.

Figure I. Yarn traverse guide moulded from GF/Nylon 6.6.

A metal component performing a similar function in a second yarn processing machine has been replaced by a GF/Nylon 6.6 part with equal success. Traditionally the use of heat treated steel was necessary to provide the mechanical performance but inertia and lubrication problems led to excessive wear between guide body and traverse spindle. The thermoplastic replacement weighs only a sixth of the metal part and the cost saving by the introduction of injection moulding is almost 80% coupled with improved performance and reduced maintenance.

Mass of steel guide	=	17.91 g
Mass of thermoplastic guide	=	2.92 g
Steel component cost	=	£3.00/item
Thermoplastic component cost	=	£0.60/item

Distributor Tube and Seal Piece for Cigarette Manufacturing Machine

Two components moulded from graphite fibre reinforced thermoplastic are in production for machine associated with cigarette manufacture. The machine conveys filter plugs from a centralised position to individual cigarette making machines. Filter rods are transmitted through distributor tubes in a rotor module to the individual cigarette assembly units. The distributor tube (Figure 2) and a second component, the seal piece, are manufactured from GF/thermoplastic. Both parts are in contact with hardened steel faces in the rotor module, rotating at 100 rpm. The excellent wear properties of the GFRP against steel offers considerable advantage, extending component lifetime.

Figure 2. Distributor tube moulded from GF/Nylon 6.6.

The distributor tube was previously manufactured from unreinforced Nylon II which built up static electricity to such an extent that the filter rods were arrested in the tube. Graphite fibre reinforced Nylon 6.6 successfully conducts all static away from the part and allows free flow of filters. Attempts were also made to manufacture the part from an aluminium casting with subsequent machining but this proved both difficult and expensive. A cost comparison is given in Table 4.

ALUMINIUM		GRAPHITE FIBRE/NYLON 6.6	
	£		£
Bought-in casting)		Raw Material	1.20
Shaw process)	6.00	Moulding cost	0.33
Machining operations	10.27	Machining operations	1.93
Energy costs (machining)	0.06	Inserts	0.50
		Tool cost amortization	1.00
		Energy cost (machining and moulding)	0.04
Total	<u>16.33</u>	Total	<u>5.00</u>

Table 4. Cost comparison for production of distributor tube. (8)

Knitting Elements for Pile Fabric Machine

The Locstitch machine is designed for the high speed production of looped pile fabric at a rate 10 to 20 times greater than conventional weaving. The process embodies a novel sewing and knitting action involving sewing needles and looper blades to insert pile on both sides of a base fabric. Sewing and loop forming is effected by low inertia elements and bars moving in high speed orbital and reciprocating motions at 750 cycles/minute. The bars up to 2.5 metres long, are constructed from strips of pultrusion bonded each side of a plastic core forming a slot into which the needle or looper sections are inserted. Stiffness, low inertia and dimensional stability are critical for efficient operation and the performance achieved with graphite fibre pultrusion is superior to the other fabrication techniques evaluated for this new machine. The individual steel needles and looper blades are encapsulated in Nylon 6.6 reinforced with graphite fibre to form short sections suitable for slotting in bar assemblies. GFRP encapsulations provide dimensional stability in operation together with the necessary mechanical performance at only a fraction of the mass of the all-metal alternative. In addition the precision processability of the reinforced thermoplastic enables close tolerance to be held by virtue of low mould shrinkage.

Figure 3. Knitting bar assembly for the Locstitch machine.

Weaving Loom Picking Stick

The picking stick activates the reciprocating motion of a shuttle in a weaving loom. Each loom has two sticks, one either side, driving the shuttle back and forth carrying a weft across the fibre warp. Figure 4 shows a closeup of a graphite picking stick on a Northrop Sensamatic loom. The stick on this particular loom operates at 100 cycles per minute accelerating a wooden shuttle of mass 0.5 kgs to 13.5 metres/second over 0.3 metres in each cycle. Previously made of densified laminated wood, the stick had a typical life of 3 to 6 months. The use of pultruded graphite sticks weighing only a third of the wooden sticks have created potential for a 10% machine speed increase. In addition, the stick lifetime of up to three years has introduced operating cost savings by virtue of lower maintenance and reduced down-time.

Graphite pultruded sticks are now supplied as original equipment by a major European manufacturer producing a range of modern high speed looms. Although the composite sticks cost 20 to 30 times more than the cheap wooden sticks, the advantages achieved in performance leading to increased productivity can be clearly demonstrated. Based on a continuous loom operation at speeds in excess of 200 picks/minute, the performance advantages can be summarised:-

- Reduction in inertia. Mass of stick reduced from 1.2 kgs to 0.7 kg requiring less energy for activation.

- More efficient picking action. The graphite stick can be accelerated more evenly and has better elastic recovery. This generates less pressure on the shuttle head decreasing from 137 kPa for the wooden stick to 101 kPa. A 2-3% increase in shuttle speed is also achieved.
- Increased service life. The operating lifetime is lengthened from approximately 6 months to an estimated 6-7 years. During 5 years operation at 60-90 million picks/year no fatigue failures have been observed.
- Machine down-time reduced from 10% to 3%.

Figure 4. Graphite Composite Picking Stick on Weaving Loom.

Valve Block for Chemical Plant

Graphite fibre reinforced polyvinylidene difluoride is used in a new all-plastic system of pipework and control gear for handling particularly hazardous and corrosive chemicals. The mechanical performance of chemically resistant PVDF is improved in several respects by including graphite fibre reinforcement. The improved stiffness, strength and surface hardness provide the ideal balance of properties for application of the material where dimensional and thermal stability is required in addition to the inherent chemical and thermal resistance of the polymer. The complex shaped blocks are injection moulded on conventional equipment and used together with other non-reinforced PVDF components in pipework systems handling chemicals such as Chlorine, Bromine, Boron Trifluoride, Hydrofluoric Acid at temperatures up to 80°C and pressures of 12 atmospheres.

One of the most important features of the new system is cost and according to the manufacturers the items moulded in graphite fibre reinforced PVDF can be produced for less than half the cost of metal components.

Wire Handling Equipment

Northampton Machinery Ltd have incorporated graphite fibre composite components in their regular production of high speed wire handling equipment. The component is used in a double twist wire bunching machine which twists copper strands into a single conductor (Figure 5). Graphite composite bows, 2 per machine, replace high tensile steel components and enable twisting speeds of 2,000 rpm to be operated without the problems normally encountered with steel bows at above 1,500 rpm. The GFRP components are compression moulded from unidirectional prepreg. The use of graphite fibre has enabled the bow to be redesigned with increased stiffness, reduced weight and cheaper fabrication technique compared with the conventional component machined from steel. An improvement in productivity is also achieved by virtue of increased operating speeds and the ability to handle heavier copper wire.

Figure 5. Composite bow in wire stranding machine.

Future Prospects

The graphite fibre reinforced plastics now available are allowing industrial designers to challenge conventional materials in performance and cost effectiveness. Recognition of the products as engineering materials is becoming established and the prospects for continued expansion, both in terms of area of application and volume usage, look good.

Whilst commercial applications have dominated the market over the past three years there is strong evidence that industrial uses will determine the ultimate market size in the 1980's.

Price trends, related to time and volume indicate substantial reductions in basic fibre production costs which become even more significant when set against the background of inflation in industrial costs over the past five years.

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